

NATIONAL BUREAU OF STATISTICS

Nigerian Domestic and Foreign Debt

(Q2 2020)

Report Date: September 2020

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Nigerian States and Federal Debt Stock data as at 30th June 2020 reflected that the country's total public debt portfolio stood at N31.01trn.

Further disaggregation of Nigeria's total public debt showed that N11.36trn or 36.65% of the debt was external while N19.65trn or 63.35% of the debt was domestic.

Total States and FCT domestic debt was put at N4.19trillion with Lagos state accounting for 11.77% of the debt stock while Yobe State has the least debt stock in this category with a contribution of 0.70%.

Important Notes:

1. Domestic Debt Stock for Twenty Eight (28) States: Abia, Adamawa, Akwa Ibom, Anambra, Bauchi, Bayelsa, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamfara and the FCT as at June 30, 2020.
2. Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State were as at December 31, 2018

Land Area: 2,440 sq mi

Population: 3,616,382

Total FAAC Allocation 2019

N52,039,868,624.86

Total IGR As At Full Year 2019

N14,769,307,658.56

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT JUNE 30, 2020

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2020

N92,806,570,546.03

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2019

N68,003,077,437.81

% ANNUAL CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK / STATE, Q2, 2020 & Q2, 2019

0.4

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q2 2020

2.22

STATES, FCT AND FEDERAL GOVERNMENTS' EXTERNAL DEBT STOCK AS AT 30TH JUNE, 2020

Multilateral

\$87,154,702.46

Bilateral (AFD)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW)

Commercial (EUROBONDS & DIASPORA BONDS)

TOTAL

\$87,154,702.46

Important Notes:

- Domestic Debt Stock for Twenty Eight (28) States: Abia, Adamawa, Akwa Ibom, Anambra, Bauchi, Bayelsa, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamfara and the FCT as at June 30, 2020.
- Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State were as at December 31, 2018

Land Area: 14, 254 sq mi

Population: 4,111,706

Total FAAC Allocation 2019

N48,338,702,097.28

Total IGR As At Full Year 2019

N9,232,405,633.53

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT JUNE 30, 2020

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2020

N100,599,569,235.97

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2019

N95,219,782,086.14

% ANNUAL CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q2, 2020 & Q2, 2019

0.1

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q2 2020

2.40

STATES, FCT AND FEDERAL GOVERNMENTS' EXTERNAL DEBT STOCK AS AT 30TH JUNE, 2020

Multilateral

\$98,976,511.58

Bilateral (AFD)

\$6,500,000.00

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW)

Commercial (EUROBONDS & DIASPORA BONDS)

TOTAL \$105,476,511.58

Important Notes:

- Domestic Debt Stock for Twenty Eight (28) States: Abia, Adamawa, Akwa Ibom, Anambra, Bauchi, Bayelsa, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamfara and the FCT as at June 30, 2020.
- Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State were as at December 31, 2018

Land Area: 2,734 sq mi

Population: 5,272,029

Total FAAC Allocation 2019

N171,975,537,274.47

Total IGR As At Full Year 2019

N32,291,014,771.52

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT JUNE 30, 2020

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2020

N239,209,746,919.94

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2019

N206,414,472,059.83

% ANNUAL CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q2, 2020 & Q2, 2019

0.2

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q2 2020

5.71

STATES, FCT AND FEDERAL GOVERNMENTS' EXTERNAL DEBT STOCK AS AT 30TH JUNE, 2020

Multilateral

\$46,619,779.74

Bilateral (AFD)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW)

Commercial (EUROBONDS & DIASPORA BONDS)

TOTAL

\$46,619,779.74

Important Notes:

- Domestic Debt Stock for Twenty Eight (28) States: Abia, Adamawa, Akwa Ibom, Anambra, Bauchi, Bayelsa, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamfara and the FCT as at June 30, 2020.
- Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State were as at December 31, 2018

Land Area: 1,870 sq mi

Population: 5,356,592

Total FAAC Allocation 2019

N53,893,862,221.01

Total IGR As At Full Year 2019

N26,369,195,864.89

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT JUNE 30, 2020

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2020

N59,013,845,976.50

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2019

N33,431,158,600.07

% ANNUAL CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q2, 2020 & Q2, 2019

0.8

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q2 2020

1.41

STATES, FCT AND FEDERAL GOVERNMENTS' EXTERNAL DEBT STOCK AS AT 30TH JUNE, 2020

Multilateral

\$115,886,392.46

Bilateral (AFD)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW)

Commercial (EUROBONDS & DIASPORA BONDS)

TOTAL \$115,886,392.46

Important Notes:

- Domestic Debt Stock for Twenty Eight (28) States: Abia, Adamawa, Akwa Ibom, Anambra, Bauchi, Bayelsa, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamfara and the FCT as at June 30, 2020.
- Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State were as at December 31, 2018

Land Area: 18, 965 sq mi

Population: 6,286,719

Total FAAC Allocation 2019

N52,357,124,339.87

Total IGR As At Full Year 2019

N11,696,955,884.75

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT JUNE 30, 2020

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2020

N97,933,063,584.67

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2019

N97,502,601,723.17

% ANNUAL CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q2, 2020 & Q2, 2019

0.0

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q2 2020

2.34

STATES, FCT AND FEDERAL GOVERNMENTS' EXTERNAL DEBT STOCK AS AT 30TH JUNE, 2020

Multilateral

\$129,449,049.24

Bilateral (AFD)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW)

Commercial (EUROBONDS & DIASPORA BONDS)

TOTAL \$129,449,049.24

Important Notes:

- Domestic Debt Stock for Twenty Eight (28) States: Abia, Adamawa, Akwa Ibom, Anambra, Bauchi, Bayelsa, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamfara and the FCT as at June 30, 2020.
- Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State were as at December 31, 2018

Land Area: 8,150 sq mi

Population: 2,204,648

Total FAAC Allocation 2019

N140,129,363,936.74

Total IGR As At Full Year 2019

N16,342,762,531.98

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT JUNE 30, 2020

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2020

N150,057,580,348.08

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2019

N133,339,375,587.91

% ANNUAL CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q2, 2020 & Q2, 2019

0.1

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q2 2020

3.58

STATES, FCT AND FEDERAL GOVERNMENTS' EXTERNAL DEBT STOCK AS AT 30TH JUNE, 2020

Multilateral

\$51,312,525.84

Bilateral (AFD)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW)

Commercial (EUROBONDS & DIASPORA BONDS)

TOTAL

\$51,312,525.84

Important Notes:

- Domestic Debt Stock for Twenty Eight (28) States: Abia, Adamawa, Akwa Ibom, Anambra, Bauchi, Bayelsa, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamfara and the FCT as at June 30, 2020.
- Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State were as at December 31, 2018

Land Area: 13,150 sq m

Population: 5,553,037

Total FAAC Allocation 2019

N54,340,296,718.03

Total IGR As At Full Year 2019

N17,850,480,389.57

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT JUNE 30, 2020

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2020

N128,504,831,985.51

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2019

N96,905,502,591.02

% ANNUAL CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q2, 2020 & Q2, 2019

0.3

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q2 2020

3.07

STATES, FCT AND FEDERAL GOVERNMENTS' EXTERNAL DEBT STOCK AS AT 30TH JUNE, 2020

Multilateral

\$29,069,437.68

Bilateral (AFD)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW)

Commercial (EUROBONDS & DIASPORA BONDS)

TOTAL

\$29,069,437.68

Important Notes:

- Domestic Debt Stock for Twenty Eight (28) States: Abia, Adamawa, Akwa Ibom, Anambra, Bauchi, Bayelsa, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamfara and the FCT as at June 30, 2020.
- Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State were as at December 31, 2018

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2020

BORNO STATE

Land Area: 22, 316 sq mi

Population: 5,635,544

Total FAAC Allocation 2019

N61,713,490,791.62

Total IGR As At Full Year 2019

N8,175,248,326.42

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT JUNE 30, 2020

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2020

N90,369,619,974.97

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2019

N86,861,555,192.24

% ANNUAL CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q2, 2020 & Q2, 2019

0.0

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q2 2020

2.16

STATES, FCT AND FEDERAL GOVERNMENTS' EXTERNAL DEBT STOCK AS AT 30TH JUNE, 2020

Multilateral

\$20,020,197.01

Bilateral (AFD)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW)

Commercial (EUROBONDS & DIASPORA BONDS)

TOTAL

\$20,020,197.01

Important Notes:

- Domestic Debt Stock for Twenty Eight (28) States: Abia, Adamawa, Akwa Ibom, Anambra, Bauchi, Bayelsa, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamfara and the FCT as at June 30, 2020.
- Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State were as at December 31, 2018

Land Area: 7,782 sq mi

Population: 3,741,838

Total FAAC Allocation 2019

N36,312,879,237.96

Total IGR As At Full Year 2019

N22,597,063,882.55

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT JUNE 30, 2020

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2020

N165,019,082,432.50

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2019

N168,819,230,129.37

% ANNUAL CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q2, 2020 & Q2, 2019

0.0

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q2 2020

3.94

STATES, FCT AND FEDERAL GOVERNMENTS' EXTERNAL DEBT STOCK AS AT 30TH JUNE, 2020

Multilateral

\$107,281,922.84

Bilateral (AFD)

\$43,900,000.00

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW)

\$21,464,442.18

Commercial (EUROBONDS & DIASPORA BONDS)

TOTAL \$172,646,365.02

Important Notes:

- Domestic Debt Stock for Twenty Eight (28) States: Abia, Adamawa, Akwa Ibom, Anambra, Bauchi, Bayelsa, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamfara and the FCT as at June 30, 2020.
- Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State were as at December 31, 2018

Land Area: 6,833 sq mi

Population: 5,460,311

Total FAAC Allocation 2019

N219,282,893,930.70

Total IGR As At Full Year 2019

N64,678,796,991.57

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT JUNE 30, 2020

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2020

N235,860,479,518.82

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2019

N233,564,158,885.47

% ANNUAL CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q2, 2020 & Q2, 2019

0.0

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q2 2020

5.63

STATES, FCT AND FEDERAL GOVERNMENTS' EXTERNAL DEBT STOCK AS AT 30TH JUNE, 2020

Multilateral

\$53,856,648.90

Bilateral (AFD)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW)

Commercial (EUROBONDS & DIASPORA BONDS)

TOTAL

\$53,856,648.90

Important Notes:

- Domestic Debt Stock for Twenty Eight (28) States: Abia, Adamawa, Akwa Ibom, Anambra, Bauchi, Bayelsa, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamfara and the FCT as at June 30, 2020.
- Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State were as at December 31, 2018

Land Area: 2,136 sq mi

Population: 2,791,167

Total FAAC Allocation 2019

N44,627,158,742.33

Total IGR As At Full Year 2019

N7,455,294,676.59

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT JUNE 30, 2020

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2020

N41,273,963,348.58

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2019

N42,053,162,874.44

% ANNUAL CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q2, 2020 & Q2, 2019

0.0

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q2 2020

0.99

STATES, FCT AND FEDERAL GOVERNMENTS' EXTERNAL DEBT STOCK AS AT 30TH JUNE, 2020

Multilateral

\$59,127,695.49

Bilateral (AFD)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW)

Commercial (EUROBONDS & DIASPORA BONDS)

TOTAL

\$59,127,695.49

Important Notes:

- Domestic Debt Stock for Twenty Eight (28) States: Abia, Adamawa, Akwa Ibom, Anambra, Bauchi, Bayelsa, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamfara and the FCT as at June 30, 2020.
- Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State were as at December 31, 2018

Land Area: 6,873 sq mi

Population: 4,109,499

Total FAAC Allocation 2019

N64,679,690,145.36

Total IGR As At Full Year 2019

N29,478,406,024.31

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT JUNE 30, 2020

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2020

N82,916,811,325.65

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2019

N84,002,644,092.96

% ANNUAL CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q2, 2020 & Q2, 2019

0.0

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q2 2020

1.98

STATES, FCT AND FEDERAL GOVERNMENTS' EXTERNAL DEBT STOCK AS AT 30TH JUNE, 2020

Multilateral

\$245,192,506.17

Bilateral (AFD)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW)

Commercial (EUROBONDS & DIASPORA BONDS)

TOTAL \$245,192,506.17

Important Notes:

- Domestic Debt Stock for Twenty Eight (28) States: Abia, Adamawa, Akwa Ibom, Anambra, Bauchi, Bayelsa, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamfara and the FCT as at June 30, 2020.
- Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State were as at December 31, 2018

Land Area: 2,453 sq mi

Population: 3,157,552

Total FAAC Allocation 2019

N41,286,185,929.89

Total IGR As At Full Year 2019

N8,546,875,648.24

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT JUNE 30, 2020

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2020

N77,072,844,596.55

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2019

N86,905,756,443.45

% ANNUAL CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q2, 2020 & Q2, 2019

0.1

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q2 2020

1.84

STATES, FCT AND FEDERAL GOVERNMENTS' EXTERNAL DEBT STOCK AS AT 30TH JUNE, 2020

Multilateral

\$90,702,124.75

Bilateral (AFD)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW)

Commercial (EUROBONDS & DIASPORA BONDS)

TOTAL \$90,702,124.75

Important Notes:

- Domestic Debt Stock for Twenty Eight (28) States: Abia, Adamawa, Akwa Ibom, Anambra, Bauchi, Bayelsa, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamfara and the FCT as at June 30, 2020.
- Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State were as at December 31, 2018

Land Area: 2,765 sq mi

Population: 4,263,786

Total FAAC Allocation 2019

N51,984,942,970.06

Total IGR As At Full Year 2019

N31,069,466,913.00

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT JUNE 30, 2020

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2020

N62,436,497,337.43

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2019

N60,151,622,506.87

% ANNUAL CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q2, 2020 & Q2, 2019

0.0

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q2 2020

1.49

STATES, FCT AND FEDERAL GOVERNMENTS' EXTERNAL DEBT STOCK AS AT 30TH JUNE, 2020

Multilateral

\$108,558,813.78

Bilateral (AFD)

\$6,500,000.00

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW)

Commercial (EUROBONDS & DIASPORA BONDS)

TOTAL \$115,058,813.78

Important Notes:

- Domestic Debt Stock for Twenty Eight (28) States: Abia, Adamawa, Akwa Ibom, Anambra, Bauchi, Bayelsa, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamfara and the FCT as at June 30, 2020.
- Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State were as at December 31, 2018

Land Area: 7, 246 sq mi

Population: 3,140,189

Total FAAC Allocation 2019

N41,019,881,265.47

Total IGR As At Full Year 2019

N6,803,064,814.10

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT JUNE 30, 2020

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2020

N90,503,282,526.59

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2019

N79,634,209,227.24

% ANNUAL CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q2, 2020 & Q2, 2019

0.1

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q2 2020

2.16

STATES, FCT AND FEDERAL GOVERNMENTS' EXTERNAL DEBT STOCK AS AT 30TH JUNE, 2020

Multilateral

\$35,200,627.45

Bilateral (AFD)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW)

Commercial (EUROBONDS & DIASPORA BONDS)

TOTAL

\$35,200,627.45

Important Notes:

- Domestic Debt Stock for Twenty Eight (28) States: Abia, Adamawa, Akwa Ibom, Anambra, Bauchi, Bayelsa, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamfara and the FCT as at June 30, 2020.
- Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State were as at December 31, 2018

Land Area: 2,140 sq mi

Population: 5,214,833

Total FAAC Allocation 2019

N56,086,098,287.13

Total IGR As At Full Year 2019

N16,095,299,620.59

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT JUNE 30, 2020

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2020

N158,174,623,598.44

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2019

N148,598,063,157.77

% ANNUAL CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q2, 2020 & Q2, 2019

0.1

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q2 2020

3.78

STATES, FCT AND FEDERAL GOVERNMENTS' EXTERNAL DEBT STOCK AS AT 30TH JUNE, 2020

Multilateral

\$23,306,075.58

Bilateral (AFD)

\$27,911,517.88

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW)

Commercial (EUROBONDS & DIASPORA BONDS)

TOTAL

\$51,217,593.46

Important Notes:

- Domestic Debt Stock for Twenty Eight (28) States: Abia, Adamawa, Akwa Ibom, Anambra, Bauchi, Bayelsa, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamfara and the FCT as at June 30, 2020.
- Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State were as at December 31, 2018

Land Area: 8,940 sq mi

Population: 5,640,592

Total FAAC Allocation 2019

N58,858,181,316.18

Total IGR As At Full Year 2019

N12,926,658,146.29

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT JUNE 30, 2020

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2020

N36,039,966,666.27

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2019

N38,673,319,242.36

% ANNUAL CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q2, 2020 & Q2, 2019

0.1

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q2 2020

0.86

STATES, FCT AND FEDERAL GOVERNMENTS' EXTERNAL DEBT STOCK AS AT 30TH JUNE, 2020

Multilateral

\$29,555,191.42

Bilateral (AFD)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW)

Commercial (EUROBONDS & DIASPORA BONDS)

TOTAL

\$29,555,191.42

Important Notes:

- Domestic Debt Stock for Twenty Eight (28) States: Abia, Adamawa, Akwa Ibom, Anambra, Bauchi, Bayelsa, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamfara and the FCT as at June 30, 2020.
- Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State were as at December 31, 2018

Land Area: 17,781 sq mi

Population: 7,976,735

Total FAAC Allocation 2019

N67,100,907,303.95

Total IGR As At Full Year 2019

N44,956,576,583.38

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT JUNE 30, 2020

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2020

N72,503,331,825.58

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2019

N97,264,280,664.14

% ANNUAL CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q2, 2020 & Q2, 2019

0.3

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q2 2020

1.73

STATES, FCT AND FEDERAL GOVERNMENTS' EXTERNAL DEBT STOCK AS AT 30TH JUNE, 2020

Multilateral

\$554,543,449.75

Bilateral (AFD)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW)

\$15,535,692.17

Commercial (EUROBONDS & DIASPORA BONDS)

TOTAL \$570,079,141.92

Important Notes:

- Domestic Debt Stock for Twenty Eight (28) States: Abia, Adamawa, Akwa Ibom, Anambra, Bauchi, Bayelsa, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamfara and the FCT as at June 30, 2020.
- Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State were as at December 31, 2018

Land Area: 7,773 sq mi

Population: 12,591,871

Total FAAC Allocation 2019

N82,485,067,955.07

Total IGR As At Full Year 2019

N40,593,701,332.48

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT JUNE 30, 2020

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2020

N116,999,956,070.87

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2019

N117,339,436,693.47

% ANNUAL CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q2, 2020 & Q2, 2019

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q2 2020

STATES, FCT AND FEDERAL GOVERNMENTS' EXTERNAL DEBT STOCK AS AT 30TH JUNE, 2020

Multilateral

\$60,485,778.07

Bilateral (AFD)

\$3,369,600.00

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW)

Commercial (EUROBONDS & DIASPORA BONDS)

TOTAL \$63,855,378.07

Important Notes:

- Domestic Debt Stock for Twenty Eight (28) States: Abia, Adamawa, Akwa Ibom, Anambra, Bauchi, Bayelsa, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamfara and the FCT as at June 30, 2020.
- Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State were as at December 31, 2018

Land Area: 9,341 sq mi

Population: 7,569,751

Total FAAC Allocation 2019

N63,256,905,564.21

Total IGR As At Full Year 2019

N8,496,742,119.00

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT JUNE 30, 2020

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2020

N44,416,331,545.82

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2019

N66,164,163,901.64

% ANNUAL CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q2, 2020 & Q2, 2019

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q2 2020

STATES, FCT AND FEDERAL GOVERNMENTS' EXTERNAL DEBT STOCK AS AT 30TH JUNE, 2020

Multilateral

\$74,995,625.44

Bilateral (AFD)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW)

Commercial (EUROBONDS & DIASPORA BONDS)

TOTAL \$74,995,625.44

Important Notes:

- Domestic Debt Stock for Twenty Eight (28) States: Abia, Adamawa, Akwa Ibom, Anambra, Bauchi, Bayelsa, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamfara and the FCT as at June 30, 2020.
- Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State were as at December 31, 2018

Land Area: 14,200 sq mi

Population: 4,286,319

Total FAAC Allocation 2019

N52,903,252,905.60

Total IGR As At Full Year 2019

N7,367,334,837.13

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT JUNE 30, 2020

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2020

N67,315,419,254.61

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2019

N59,598,378,104.63

% ANNUAL CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q2, 2020 & Q2, 2019

0.1

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q2 2020

1.61

STATES, FCT AND FEDERAL GOVERNMENTS' EXTERNAL DEBT STOCK AS AT 30TH JUNE, 2020

Multilateral

\$42,012,518.94

Bilateral (AFD)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW)

Commercial (EUROBONDS & DIASPORA BONDS)

TOTAL

\$42,012,518.94

Important Notes:

- Domestic Debt Stock for Twenty Eight (28) States: Abia, Adamawa, Akwa Ibom, Anambra, Bauchi, Bayelsa, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamfara and the FCT as at June 30, 2020.
- Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State were as at December 31, 2018

Land Area: 11,519 sq mi

Population: 4,324,074

Total FAAC Allocation 2019

N52,336,274,793.13

Total IGR As At Full Year 2019

N16,389,026,388.86

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT JUNE 30, 2020

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2020

N73,314,904,696.35

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2019

N105,135,912,916.85

% ANNUAL CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q2, 2020 & Q2, 2019

0.3

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q2 2020

1.75

STATES, FCT AND FEDERAL GOVERNMENTS' EXTERNAL DEBT STOCK AS AT 30TH JUNE, 2020

Multilateral

\$28,629,302.18

Bilateral (AFD)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW)

Commercial (EUROBONDS & DIASPORA BONDS)

TOTAL

\$28,629,302.18

Important Notes:

- Domestic Debt Stock for Twenty Eight (28) States: Abia, Adamawa, Akwa Ibom, Anambra, Bauchi, Bayelsa, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamfara and the FCT as at June 30, 2020.
- Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State were as at December 31, 2018

Land Area: 14, 218 sq mi

Population: 3,086,249

Total FAAC Allocation 2019

N42,432,526,858.74

Total IGR As At Full Year 2019

N30,646,731,408.92

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT JUNE 30, 2020

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2020

N63,366,236,320.99

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2019

N61,335,531,821.69

% ANNUAL CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q2, 2020 & Q2, 2019

0.0

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q2 2020

1.51

STATES, FCT AND FEDERAL GOVERNMENTS' EXTERNAL DEBT STOCK AS AT 30TH JUNE, 2020

Multilateral

\$43,426,265.98

Bilateral (AFD)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW)

Commercial (EUROBONDS & DIASPORA BONDS)

TOTAL

\$43,426,265.98

Important Notes:

- Domestic Debt Stock for Twenty Eight (28) States: Abia, Adamawa, Akwa Ibom, Anambra, Bauchi, Bayelsa, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamfara and the FCT as at June 30, 2020.
- Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State were as at December 31, 2018

Land Area: 1,381 sq mi

Population: 12,100,616

Total FAAC Allocation 2019

N117,883,619,963.70

Total IGR As At Full Year 2019

N398,732,246,493.38

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT JUNE 30, 2020

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2020

N493,318,231,673.72

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2019

N479,047,606,006.32

% ANNUAL CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q2, 2020 & Q2, 2019

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q2 2020

STATES, FCT AND FEDERAL GOVERNMENTS' EXTERNAL DEBT STOCK AS AT 30TH JUNE, 2020

Multilateral

\$1,117,394,751.98

Bilateral (AFD)

\$143,830,000.00

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW)

Commercial (EUROBONDS & DIASPORA BONDS)

TOTAL \$1,261,224,751.98

Important Notes:

- Domestic Debt Stock for Twenty Eight (28) States: Abia, Adamawa, Akwa Ibom, Anambra, Bauchi, Bayelsa, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamfara and the FCT as at June 30, 2020.
- Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State were as at December 31, 2018

Land Area: 10, 470 sq mi

Population: 2,439,113

Total FAAC Allocation 2019

N44,865,859,450.71

Total IGR As At Full Year 2019

N10,858,822,422.98

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT JUNE 30, 2020

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2020

N61,299,995,407.54

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2019

N89,953,619,684.92

% ANNUAL CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q2, 2020 & Q2, 2019

(0.3)

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q2 2020

1.46

STATES, FCT AND FEDERAL GOVERNMENTS' EXTERNAL DEBT STOCK AS AT 30TH JUNE, 2020

Multilateral

\$55,823,034.28

Bilateral (AFD)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW)

Commercial (EUROBONDS & DIASPORA BONDS)

TOTAL

\$55,823,034.28

Important Notes:

- Domestic Debt Stock for Twenty Eight (28) States: Abia, Adamawa, Akwa Ibom, Anambra, Bauchi, Bayelsa, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamfara and the FCT as at June 30, 2020.
- Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State were as at December 31, 2018

Land Area: 10, 470 sq mi

Population: 5,343,260

Total FAAC Allocation 2019

N56,447,911,750.79

Total IGR As At Full Year 2019

N12,765,034,972.30

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT JUNE 30, 2020

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2020

N65,601,207,473.58

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2019

N41,792,519,380.33

% ANNUAL CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q2, 2020 & Q2, 2019

0.6

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q2 2020

1.57

STATES, FCT AND FEDERAL GOVERNMENTS' EXTERNAL DEBT STOCK AS AT 30TH JUNE, 2020

Multilateral

\$66,003,904.55

Bilateral (AFD)

\$12,500,000.00

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW)

Commercial (EUROBONDS & DIASPORA BONDS)

TOTAL

\$78,503,904.55

Important Notes:

- Domestic Debt Stock for Twenty Eight (28) States: Abia, Adamawa, Akwa Ibom, Anambra, Bauchi, Bayelsa, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamfara and the FCT as at June 30, 2020.
- Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State were as at December 31, 2018

Land Area: 6,556.23 sq mi

Population: 5,024,191

Total FAAC Allocation 2019

N38,710,634,518.43

Total IGR As At Full Year 2019

N70,922,590,495.89

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT JUNE 30, 2020

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2020

N148,772,734,071.17

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2019

N95,174,172,678.30

% ANNUAL CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q2, 2020 & Q2, 2019

0.6

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q2 2020

3.55

STATES, FCT AND FEDERAL GOVERNMENTS' EXTERNAL DEBT STOCK AS AT 30TH JUNE, 2020

Multilateral

\$89,614,146.87

Bilateral (AFD)

\$8,294,600.00

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW)

Commercial (EUROBONDS & DIASPORA BONDS)

TOTAL \$97,908,746.87

Important Notes:

- Domestic Debt Stock for Twenty Eight (28) States: Abia, Adamawa, Akwa Ibom, Anambra, Bauchi, Bayelsa, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamfara and the FCT as at June 30, 2020.
- Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State were as at December 31, 2018

Land Area: 6,000 sq mi

Population: 4,515,660

Total FAAC Allocation 2019

N57,927,048,890.29

Total IGR As At Full Year 2019

N30,135,881,918.26

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT JUNE 30, 2020

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2020

N63,677,729,196.02

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2019

N55,524,221,404.56

% ANNUAL CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q2, 2020 & Q2, 2019

0.1

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q2 2020

1.52

STATES, FCT AND FEDERAL GOVERNMENTS' EXTERNAL DEBT STOCK AS AT 30TH JUNE, 2020

Multilateral

\$74,792,475.77

Bilateral (AFD)

\$5,000,000.00

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW)

Commercial (EUROBONDS & DIASPORA BONDS)

TOTAL \$79,792,475.77

Important Notes:

- Domestic Debt Stock for Twenty Eight (28) States: Abia, Adamawa, Akwa Ibom, Anambra, Bauchi, Bayelsa, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamfara and the FCT as at June 30, 2020.
- Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State were as at December 31, 2018

Land Area: 3,572 sq mi

Population: 4,536,877

Total FAAC Allocation 2019

N24,222,272,968.41

Total IGR As At Full Year 2019

N17,922,394,523.43

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT JUNE 30, 2020

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2020

N136,125,242,955.06

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2019

N144,804,503,035.23

% ANNUAL CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q2, 2020 & Q2, 2019

(0.1)

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q2 2020

3.25

STATES, FCT AND FEDERAL GOVERNMENTS' EXTERNAL DEBT STOCK AS AT 30TH JUNE, 2020

Multilateral

\$78,140,931.31

Bilateral (AFD)

\$12,245,989.00

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW)

Commercial (EUROBONDS & DIASPORA BONDS)

TOTAL

\$90,386,920.31

Important Notes:

- Domestic Debt Stock for Twenty Eight (28) States: Abia, Adamawa, Akwa Ibom, Anambra, Bauchi, Bayelsa, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamfara and the FCT as at June 30, 2020.
- Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State were as at December 31, 2018

Land Area: 10,986 sq mi

Population: 7,540,300

Total FAAC Allocation 2019

N55,800,604,161.25

Total IGR As At Full Year 2019

N26,746,460,235.93

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT JUNE 30, 2020

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2020

N99,943,412,785.14

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2019

N99,358,565,798.52

% ANNUAL CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q2, 2020 & Q2, 2019

0.0

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q2 2020

2.39

STATES, FCT AND FEDERAL GOVERNMENTS' EXTERNAL DEBT STOCK AS AT 30TH JUNE, 2020

Multilateral

\$82,509,495.08

Bilateral (AFD)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW)

Commercial (EUROBONDS & DIASPORA BONDS)

TOTAL

\$82,509,495.08

Important Notes:

- Domestic Debt Stock for Twenty Eight (28) States: Abia, Adamawa, Akwa Ibom, Anambra, Bauchi, Bayelsa, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamfara and the FCT as at June 30, 2020.
- Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State were as at December 31, 2018

Land Area: 11, 936 sq mi

Population: 4,075,392

Total FAAC Allocation 2019

N42,224,236,190.96

Total IGR As At Full Year 2019

N16,480,111,593.83

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT JUNE 30, 2020

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2020

N127,012,622,276.11

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2019

N98,356,193,262.55

% ANNUAL CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q2, 2020 & Q2, 2019

0.3

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q2 2020

3.03

STATES, FCT AND FEDERAL GOVERNMENTS' EXTERNAL DEBT STOCK AS AT 30TH JUNE, 2020

Multilateral

\$28,126,343.15

Bilateral (AFD)

\$5,000,000.00

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW)

Commercial (EUROBONDS & DIASPORA BONDS)

TOTAL

\$33,126,343.15

Important Notes:

- Domestic Debt Stock for Twenty Eight (28) States: Abia, Adamawa, Akwa Ibom, Anambra, Bauchi, Bayelsa, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamfara and the FCT as at June 30, 2020.
- Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State were as at December 31, 2018

Land Area: 4,277 sq mi

Population: 7,023,942

Total FAAC Allocation 2019

N158,449,294,787.50

Total IGR As At Full Year 2019

N140,398,744,302.70

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT JUNE 30, 2020

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2020

N266,936,225,793.65

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2019

N266,936,225,793.65

% ANNUAL CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q2, 2020 & Q2, 2019

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q2 2020

STATES, FCT AND FEDERAL GOVERNMENTS' EXTERNAL DEBT STOCK AS AT 30TH JUNE, 2020

Multilateral

\$69,534,420.77

Bilateral (AFD)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW)

Commercial (EUROBONDS & DIASPORA BONDS)

TOTAL

\$69,534,420.77

Important Notes:

- Domestic Debt Stock for Twenty Eight (28) States: Abia, Adamawa, Akwa Ibom, Anambra, Bauchi, Bayelsa, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamfara and the FCT as at June 30, 2020.
- Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State were as at December 31, 2018

Land Area: 10,028 sq mi

Population: 4,831,152

Total FAAC Allocation 2019

N55,476,385,825.97

Total IGR As At Full Year 2019

N19,005,093,541.11

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT JUNE 30, 2020

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2020

N48,089,793,082.99

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2019

N33,509,692,266.79

% ANNUAL CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q2, 2020 & Q2, 2019

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q2 2020

STATES, FCT AND FEDERAL GOVERNMENTS' EXTERNAL DEBT STOCK AS AT 30TH JUNE, 2020

Multilateral

\$34,661,496.13

Bilateral (AFD)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW)

Commercial (EUROBONDS & DIASPORA BONDS)

TOTAL

\$34,661,496.13

Important Notes:

- Domestic Debt Stock for Twenty Eight (28) States: Abia, Adamawa, Akwa Ibom, Anambra, Bauchi, Bayelsa, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamfara and the FCT as at June 30, 2020.
- Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State were as at December 31, 2018

Land Area: 21, 032 sq mi

Population: 2,968,132

Total FAAC Allocation 2019

N46,515,352,151.03

Total IGR As At Full Year 2019

N6,533,106,447.27

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT JUNE 30, 2020

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2020

N122,746,246,998.60

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2019

N73,466,840,201.25

% ANNUAL CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q2, 2020 & Q2, 2019

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q2 2020

STATES, FCT AND FEDERAL GOVERNMENTS' EXTERNAL DEBT STOCK AS AT 30TH JUNE, 2020

Multilateral

\$34,641,916.22

Bilateral (AFD)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW)

Commercial (EUROBONDS & DIASPORA BONDS)

TOTAL

\$34,641,916.22

Important Notes:

- Domestic Debt Stock for Twenty Eight (28) States: Abia, Adamawa, Akwa Ibom, Anambra, Bauchi, Bayelsa, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamfara and the FCT as at June 30, 2020.
- Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State were as at December 31, 2018

Land Area: 17, 568 sq mi

Population: 3,163,747

Total FAAC Allocation 2019

N51,606,083,679.10

Total IGR As At Full Year 2019

N8,444,634,099.09

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT JUNE 30, 2020

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2020

N29,230,547,154.25

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2019

N27,465,573,418.77

% ANNUAL CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q2, 2020 & Q2, 2019

0.1

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q2 2020

0.70

STATES, FCT AND FEDERAL GOVERNMENTS' EXTERNAL DEBT STOCK AS AT 30TH JUNE, 2020

Multilateral

\$25,669,384.57

Bilateral (AFD)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW)

Commercial (EUROBONDS & DIASPORA BONDS)

TOTAL

\$25,669,384.57

Important Notes:

- Domestic Debt Stock for Twenty Eight (28) States: Abia, Adamawa, Akwa Ibom, Anambra, Bauchi, Bayelsa, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamfara and the FCT as at June 30, 2020.
- Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State were as at December 31, 2018

Land Area: 15,352 sq mi

Population: 4,353,533

Total FAAC Allocation 2019

N41,762,298,726.55

Total IGR As At Full Year 2019

N15,416,043,399.76

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT JUNE 30, 2020

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2020

N79,286,884,618.37

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2019

N61,716,954,035.15

% ANNUAL CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q2, 2020 & Q2, 2019

0.3

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q2 2020

1.89

STATES, FCT AND FEDERAL GOVERNMENTS' EXTERNAL DEBT STOCK AS AT 30TH JUNE, 2020

Multilateral

\$29,638,974.33

Bilateral (AFD)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW)

Commercial (EUROBONDS & DIASPORA BONDS)

TOTAL

\$29,638,974.33

Important Notes:

- Domestic Debt Stock for Twenty Eight (28) States: Abia, Adamawa, Akwa Ibom, Anambra, Bauchi, Bayelsa, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamfara and the FCT as at June 30, 2020.
- Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State were as at December 31, 2018

Land Area: 15,352 sq mi

Population: 4,353,533

Total FAAC Allocation 2019

N71,905,269,001.29

Total IGR As At Full Year 2019

N74,564,180,835.31

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT JUNE 30, 2020

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2020

N101,949,645,786.10

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2019

N132,195,733,234.70

% ANNUAL CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q2, 2020 & Q2, 2019

(0.2)

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q2 2020

2.43

STATES, FCT AND FEDERAL GOVERNMENTS' EXTERNAL DEBT STOCK AS AT 30TH JUNE, 2020

Multilateral

\$29,084,778.83

Bilateral (AFD)

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW)

Commercial (EUROBONDS & DIASPORA BONDS)

TOTAL

\$29,084,778.83

Important Notes:

- Domestic Debt Stock for Twenty Eight (28) States: Abia, Adamawa, Akwa Ibom, Anambra, Bauchi, Bayelsa, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamfara and the FCT as at June 30, 2020.
- Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State were as at December 31, 2018

Total FAAC Allocation 2019

N2,473,237,965,275.64

Total IGR As At Full Year 2019

N1,333,753,755,729.47

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT JUNE 30, 2020

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2020

N4,189,699,078,909.01

DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2019

N3,966,219,816,141.57

% ANNUAL CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q2, 2020 & Q2, 2019

% SHARE OF EACH STATE TO TOTAL DEBT STOCK, Q2 2020

STATES, FCT AND FEDERAL GOVERNMENTS' EXTERNAL DEBT STOCK AS AT 30TH JUNE, 2020

Multilateral

\$3,950,999,196.60

Bilateral (AFD)

\$275,051,706.88

Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW)

\$37,000,134.35

Commercial (EUROBONDS & DIASPORA BONDS)

TOTAL \$4,263,051,037.83

Important Notes:

- Domestic Debt Stock for Twenty Eight (28) States: Abia, Adamawa, Akwa Ibom, Anambra, Bauchi, Bayelsa, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamfara and the FCT as at June 30, 2020.
- Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State were as at December 31, 2018

STATES, FCT AND FEDERAL GOVERNMENTS' EXTERNAL DEBT STOCK AS AT 30TH JUNE, 2020

Important Notes:

- Domestic Debt Stock for Twenty Eight (28) States: Abia, Adamawa, Akwa Ibom, Anambra, Bauchi, Bayelsa, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamfara and the FCT as at June 30, 2020.
- Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State were as at December 31, 2018

STATES, FCT AND FEDERAL GOVERNMENTS' EXTERNAL DEBT STOCK AS AT 30TH JUNE, 2020

Important Notes:

- Domestic Debt Stock for Twenty Eight (28) States: Abia, Adamawa, Akwa Ibom, Anambra, Bauchi, Bayelsa, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamfara and the FCT as at June 30, 2020.
- Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State were as at December 31, 2018

PERCENTAGE OF STATES & FCT TO GRAND TOTAL

PERCENTAGE OF FGN TO GRAND TOTAL

Important Notes:

1. Domestic Debt Stock for Twenty Eight (28) States: Abia, Adamawa, Akwa Ibom, Anambra, Bauchi, Bayelsa, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamfara and the FCT as at June 30, 2020.
2. Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State were as at December 31, 2018

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2020

FEDERAL GOVERNMENT DOMESTIC DEBT STOCK BY INSTRUMENT AS AT JUNE 30, 2020

N.B: FIGURES ARE PROVISIONAL SUBJECT TO RECONCILIATION

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2020

FEDERAL GOVERNMENT DOMESTIC DEBT STOCK BY INSTRUMENT AS AT JUNE 30, 2019

FGN BONDS

N.B: FIGURES ARE PROVISIONAL SUBJECT TO RECONCILIATION

N.B: FIGURES ARE PROVISIONAL SUBJECT TO RECONCILIATION

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2020

NIGERIA'S TOTAL PUBLIC DEBT PORTFOLIO AS AT JUNE 30, 2020

PUBLIC DEBT STOCK - EXTERNAL AND DOMESTIC DEBT OF THE FGN, STATES AND FCT AS AT JUNE 30, 2020

Important Notes:

1. CBN Official Exchange Rate of US\$1 to NGN361 as at June 30, 2020 was used in converting the Domestic Debts to USD.

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2020

NIGERIA'S TOTAL PUBLIC DEBT PORTFOLIO AS AT JUNE 30, 2020

PUBLIC DEBT STOCK - EXTERNAL AND DOMESTIC DEBT OF THE FGN, STATES AND FCT AS AT JUNE 30, 2019

Important Notes:

1. CBN Official Exchange Rate of US\$1 to NGN361 as at June 30, 2020 was used in converting the Domestic Debts to USD.

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2020

NIGERIA'S TOTAL PUBLIC DEBT PORTFOLIO AS AT JUNE 30, 2020

ANNUAL PERCENTAGE INCREASE OF NIGERIA'S PUBLIC DEBT Q2, 2020 & Q2, 2019

Important Notes:

1. CBN Official Exchange Rate of US\$1 to NGN361 as at June 30, 2020 was used in converting the Domestic Debts to USD.

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2020

DOMESTIC DEBT SERVICE FOR Q2 2020

FEDERAL GOVERNMENT ACTUAL DOMESTIC DEBT SERVICE FOR SECOND QUARTER, 2020

	April	May	June	Total
NTBs				
	Interest	Interest	Interest	Interest
	N25,970,431,060.35	N5,856,405,366.18	N11,799,416,906.39	N43,626,253,332.92
FGN Bonds				
	Interest	Interest	Interest	Interest
	N202,191,929,521.11	N31,886,342,240.96	-----	N234,078,271,762.07
Treasury Bonds				
	Interest	Interest	Interest	Interest
	-----	-----	-----	N0.00
	Principal	Principal	Principal	Principal
	-----	-----	N25000000000	N25,000,000,000.00
FGN Savings Bond				
	Interest	Interest	Interest	Interest
	N162,049,612.61	N131,339,036.76	N131,907,561.70	N425,296,211.07
FGN SUKUK				
	Rentals	Rentals	Rentals	Rentals
	-----	-----	-----	-----
	Interest	Interest	Interest	Interest
	-----	-----	N7,871,971,382.59	N7,871,971,382.59
FGN Green Bond				
	Interest	Interest	Interest	Interest
	-----	-----	N1808423210	N1,808,423,210.29
TOTAL INTEREST				
	Interest	Interest	Interest	Interest
	N228,324,410,194.07	N37,874,086,643.90	N46,611,719,060.97	N312,810,215,898.94

NOTES:

- TOTAL INTEREST EXCLUDES THE SINKING FUND CHARGES OF N161,092,250.00 IN RESPECT OF TREASURY BONDS (MANAGED BY THE CBN)
- TOTAL DOMESTIC DEBT SERVICE ARE PROVISIONAL SUBJECT TO RECONCILIATION AND SIGN-OFF WITH THE CBN & OAGF

NIGERIAN DOMESTIC AND FOREIGN DEBT - Q2 2020

DOMESTIC DEBT SERVICE FOR Q2 2020

FEDERAL GOVERNMENT ACTUAL DOMESTIC DEBT SERVICE FOR SECOND QUARTER, 2019

	April	May	June	Total
NTBs				
	Interest N14,897,947,747.19	Interest N14,700,317,313.85	Interest N16,113,483,121.45	Interest N45,711,748,182.49
FGN Bonds				
	Interest N69,184,981,715.55	Interest N31,779,137,060.69	Interest N28,027,002,739.73	Interest N128,991,121,515.97
Treasury Bonds				
	Interest -----	Interest N3,125,000,000.00	Interest N3,125,000,000.00	Interest N6,250,000,000.00
	Principal -----	Principal -----	Principal -----	Principal -----
FGN Savings Bond				
	Interest N112,381,123.27	Interest N100,208,236.88	Interest N98,031,264.55	Interest N310,620,624.70
FGN SUKUK				
	Rentals -----	Rentals -----	Rentals -----	Rentals N0.00
	Interest -----	Interest -----	Interest N7,849,934,246.58	Interest N7,849,934,246.58
FGN Green Bond				
	Interest -----	Interest -----	Interest N718,532,010.96	Interest N718,532,010.96
TOTAL INTEREST				
	Interest N84,195,310,586.01	Interest N49,704,662,611.42	Interest N55,931,983,383.27	Interest N189,831,956,580.70

NOTES:

- TOTAL INTEREST EXCLUDES THE SINKING FUND CHARGES OF N161,092,250.00 IN RESPECT OF TREASURY BONDS (MANAGED BY THE CBN)
- TOTAL DOMESTIC DEBT SERVICE ARE PROVISIONAL SUBJECT TO RECONCILIATION AND SIGN-OFF WITH THE CBN & OAGF

PERCENTAGE CHANGE OF INTEREST PAYMENT IN DOMESTIC DEBT SERVICE Q1, 2020 & Q4, 2019

ACTUAL EXTERNAL DEBT SERVICE PAYMENTS APRIL - JUNE, 2020

Total

\$94,911.07

MULTILATERAL

Percentage of Total

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service	Overdue Charges Indemnity	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$61,163.45	\$17,721.59	\$13,818.84	0.00	\$78.58	\$207.43	\$615.75	\$(38.20)	\$1343.62	\$0.00

IBRD

Total

\$6,368.16

Percentage of Total

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service	Overdue Charges Indemnity	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$0.00	\$6,368.16	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00

A.D.B

Total

\$19,159.79

Percentage of Total

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service	Overdue Charges Indemnity	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$13,333.33	\$5,293.53	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$532.93	\$0.00

IFAD

Total

\$165.27

Percentage of Total

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service	Overdue Charges Indemnity	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$00.0	\$165.27	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00

A.D.F

Total **\$1,800.56** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service	Overdue Charges Indemnity	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$929.02	\$509.30	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$362.24	\$0.00

IDA

Total **\$64,539.26** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service	Overdue Charges Indemnity	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$44,812.01	\$5,220.04	\$13,809.60	\$0.00	\$78.58	\$207.43	\$0.00	\$(36.86)	\$448.45	\$0.00

EDF

Total **\$1,660.86** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service	Overdue Charges Indemnity	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$1,495.57	\$165.29	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.19

BADEA

Total **\$0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service	Overdue Charges Indemnity	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00

IDB

Total **\$1,217.17** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service	Overdue Charges Indemnity	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$593.52	\$0.00	\$9.24	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$615.75	\$(1.34)	\$0.00	\$0.00

Total

\$14,260.19

Percentage of Total

BILATERAL

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service	Overdue Charges Indemnity	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$9,107.39	\$4,221.80	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	-\$226.71	\$1,157.71	\$0.00

EXIM BANK OF CHINA

Total **\$0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service	Overdue Charges Indemnity	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00

NIGERIA COMMUNICATION SATELLITE

Total **\$0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service	Overdue Charges Indemnity	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00

NIGERIA NATIONAL PUBLIC SECURITY COMM. SYS. PROJECT

Total **\$0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service	Overdue Charges Indemnity	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00

NIGERIA RAILWAY MODERNISATION PROJECT (IDU KADUNA SECTION)

Total **\$0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service	Overdue Charges Indemnity	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00

NIGERIA RAILWAY MODERNISATION PROJECT (LAGOS - IBADAN SECTION)

Total **\$0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service	Overdue Charges Indemnity	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00

NIGERIA ABUJA LIGHT RAIL PROJECT

Total **\$0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service	Overdue Charges Indemnity	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00

NIGERIA ICT INFRASTRUCTURE BACKBONE PROJECT

Total **\$0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service	Overdue Charges Indemnity	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00

NIGERIA FOUR AIRPORT TERMINALS EXPANSION PROJECT

Total **\$0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service	Overdue Charges Indemnity	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00

NIGERIAN ZUNGERU HYDROELECTRIC PROJECT

Total **\$0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service	Overdue Charges Indemnity	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00

NIGERIAN REHABILITATION AND UPGRADING OF ABUJA-KEFFI-MAKURDI ROAD PROJECT

Total **\$0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service	Overdue Charges Indemnity	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00

EXIM BANK OF INDIA

Total **\$0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service	Overdue Charges Indemnity	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00

FRENCH DEVELOPMENT AGENCY

Total **\$14,215.85** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service	Overdue Charges Indemnity	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$9,107.39	\$4,177.46	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$(226.71)	\$1,157.71	\$0.00

JICA

Total **\$0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service	Overdue Charges Indemnity	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00

KFW

Total **\$44.34** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service	Overdue Charges Indemnity	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$0.00	\$44.34	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service	Overdue Charges Indemnity	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$0.00	\$157,012.17	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service	Overdue Charges Indemnity	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$0.00	\$148,574.67	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00

7.625% EUROBOND 2025

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service	Overdue Charges Indemnity	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$0.00	\$42,637.17	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00

6.5% EUROBOND 2027

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service	Overdue Charges Indemnity	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$0.00	\$48,750.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00

7.625% EUROBOND 2047

Total **\$57,187.50** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service	Overdue Charges Indemnity	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$0.00	\$57,187.50	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00

Total

\$8,437.50

DIASPORA BOND

Percentage of Total

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service	Overdue Charges Indemnity	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$0.00	\$8,437.50	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00

Total

\$20,859.63

OTHERS

Percentage of Total

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service	Overdue Charges Indemnity	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$0.00	\$20,859.63	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00

AGENCY FEES

Total **\$0.00** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service	Overdue Charges Indemnity	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00

OIL WARRANT

Total **\$20,859.63** | Percentage of Total **-----**

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest	Deferred Service	Overdue Charges Indemnity	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$0.00	\$20,859.63	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$0.00

Total

\$287,043.07

TOTAL

Percentage of Total

Principal	Interest Fee	Service Fee	Deferred Principal	Deferred Interest
\$70,270.84	\$199,815.19	\$13,818.84	\$0.00	\$78.58
Deferred Service	Overdue Charges Indemnity	Waiver/Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges
\$207.43	\$615.75	\$(264.91)	\$2,501.33	\$0.00

NIGERIA'S EXTERNAL DEBT STOCK AS AT JUNE 30, 2020

('million)

Sub-Total

\$16,360.14

SUB - TOTAL

Percentage of Total

Sub-Total

\$3,948.65

SUB - TOTAL

Percentage of Total

('million)

COMMERCIAL

EUROBONDS

\$10,868.35

DIASPORA BOND

\$300.00

Sub-Total

\$11,168.35

SUB - TOTAL

Percentage of Total

GRAND TOTAL

\$31,477.14

Percentage of Total

METHODOLOGY

Data is supplied administratively by the Debt Management Office, Nigeria and verified and validated by the National Bureau of Statistics, Nigeria.

NIGERIA'S TOTAL PUBLIC DEBT PORTFOLIO AS AT JUNE 30, 2020										Annual Percentage Increase of Nigeria's Public Debt Q2, 2020 & Q2, 2019	
Public Debt Stock - External and Domestic Debt of the FGN, States and FCT as at June 30, 2020					Public Debt Stock - External and Domestic Debt of the FGN, States and FCT as at June 30, 2019					USD	NGN
	Debt Category	Amount Outstanding (US\$'M)	Amount Outstanding (N'M)	% of Total		Debt Category	Amount Outstanding (US\$'M)	Amount Outstanding (N'M)	% of Total		
A.	Total External Debt	31,477.13	11,363,243.93	36.65%	A.	Total External Debt	27,162.63	8,322,629.83	32.38%	15.9%	36.5%
	FGN Only	27,214.08	9,824,282.88	31.68%		FGN Only	22,887.96	7,012,870.94	27.29%	18.9%	40.1%
	States & FCT	4,263.05	1,538,961.05	4.96%		States & FCT	4,274.67	1,309,758.89	5.10%	-0.3%	17.5%
B.	Total Domestic Debt	54,419.39	19,645,398.21	63.35%	B.	Total Domestic Debt	56,720.03	17,379,015.91	67.62%	-4.1%	13.0%
	FGN Only	42,813.57	15,455,699.13	49.84%		FGN Only	43,775.44	13,412,796.09	52.19%	-2.2%	15.2%
	States & FCT	11,605.81	4,189,699.08	13.51%		States & FCT	12,944.58	3,966,219.82	15.43%	-10.3%	5.6%
C.	Total Public Debt(A+B)	85,896.52	31,008,642.14	100%	C.	Total Public Debt(A+B)	83,882.66	25,701,645.74	100%	2.4%	20.6%

Note: I. CBN Official Exchange Rate of US\$1 to NGN361 as at June 30, 2020 was used in converting the Domestic Debts to USD.

Federal Government Domestic Debt Stock by Instrument as at June 30, 2020			Federal Government Domestic Debt Stock by Instrument as at June 30, 2019			Debt Instruments growth rate between Q2 2020 and Q2 2019
Instruments	Amounts in Naira	% Share of each Debt Instrument	Instruments	Amounts in Naira	% Share of each Debt Instrument	
FGN Bonds	11,241,302,024,592.00	72.73%	FGN Bonds	9,691,417,043,592.00	72.26	0.16
FGN Savings Bond	12,984,652,000.00	0.08%	FGN Savings Bond	10,431,836,000.00	0.08	0.24
FGN Sukuk	362,557,000,000.00	2.35%	FGN Sukuk	200,000,000,000.00	1.49	0.81
Green Bond	25,690,000,000.00	0.17%	Green Bond	25,690,000,000.00	0.19	-
Nigerian Treasury Bills	2,760,436,493,000.00	17.86%	Nigerian Treasury Bills	2,651,514,042,000.00	19.77	0.04
Nigerian Treasury Bonds	100,988,000,000.00	0.65%	Nigerian Treasury Bonds	125,988,000,000.00	0.94	(0.20)
Promissory Notes	951,740,961,939.00	6.16%	Promissory Notes	707,755,166,029.00	5.28	0.34
TOTAL	15,455,699,131,531.00	100.00%	TOTAL	13,412,796,087,621.00	100.00	0.15
N.B: FIGURES ARE PROVISIONAL SUBJECT TO RECONCILIATION						

DOMESTIC DEBT DATA FOR THE 36 STATES OF THE FEDERATION AND THE FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY AS AT JUNE 30, 2020				Description of State Debt Status	
AMOUNT IN NAIRA PROVISIONAL					
SN	STATE	DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2020	DEBT STOCK AS AT Q2, 2019	% ANNUAL CHANGE IN DEBT STOCK/ STATE, Q2,2020 & Q2,2019	% Share of each State to Total Debt Stock, Q2 2020
1	ABIA	92,806,570,546.03	68,003,077,437.81	0.4	2.22%
2	ADAMAWA	100,599,569,235.97	95,219,782,086.14	0.1	2.40%
3	AKWA IBOM	239,209,746,919.94	206,414,472,059.83	0.2	5.71%
4	ANAMBRA	59,013,845,976.50	33,431,158,600.07	0.8	1.41%
5	BAUCHI	97,933,063,584.67	97,502,601,723.17	0.0	2.34%
6	BAYELSA	150,057,580,348.08	133,339,375,587.91	0.1	3.58%
7	BENUE	128,504,831,985.51	96,905,502,591.02	0.3	3.07%
8	BORNO	90,369,619,974.97	86,861,555,192.24	0.0	2.16%
9	CROSS-RIVER	165,019,082,432.50	168,819,230,129.37	(0.0)	3.94%
10	DELTA	235,860,479,518.82	233,564,158,885.47	0.0	5.63%
11	EBONYI	41,273,963,348.58	42,053,162,874.44	(0.0)	0.99%
12	EDO	82,916,811,325.65	84,002,644,092.96	(0.0)	1.98%
13	EKITI	77,072,844,596.55	86,905,756,443.45	(0.1)	1.84%
14	ENUGU	62,436,497,337.43	60,151,622,506.87	0.0	1.49%
15	GOMBE	90,503,282,526.59	79,634,209,227.24	0.1	2.16%
16	IMO	158,174,623,598.44	148,598,063,157.77	0.1	3.78%
17	JIGAWA	36,039,966,666.27	38,673,319,242.36	(0.1)	0.86%
18	KADUNA	72,503,331,825.58	97,264,280,664.14	(0.3)	1.73%
19	KANO	116,999,956,070.87	117,339,436,693.47	(0.0)	2.79%
20	KATSINA	44,416,331,545.82	66,164,163,901.64	(0.3)	1.06%
21	KEBBI	67,315,419,254.61	59,598,378,104.63	0.1	1.61%
22	KOGI	73,314,904,696.35	105,135,912,916.85	(0.3)	1.75%
23	KWARA	63,366,236,320.99	61,335,531,821.69	0.0	1.51%
24	LAGOS	493,318,231,673.72	479,047,606,006.32	0.0	11.77%
25	NASARAWA	61,299,995,407.54	89,953,619,684.92	(0.3)	1.46%
26	NIGER	65,601,207,473.58	41,792,519,380.33	0.6	1.57%
27	OGUN	148,772,734,071.17	95,174,172,678.30	0.6	3.55%
28	ONDO	63,677,729,196.02	55,524,221,404.56	0.1	1.52%
29	OSUN	136,125,242,955.06	144,804,503,035.23	(0.1)	3.25%
30	OYO	99,943,412,785.14	99,358,565,798.52	0.0	2.39%
31	PLATEAU	127,012,622,276.11	98,356,193,262.55	0.3	3.03%
32	RIVERS	266,936,225,793.65	266,936,225,793.65	0.0	6.37%
33	SOKOTO	48,089,793,082.99	33,509,692,266.79	0.4	1.15%
34	TARABA	122,746,246,998.60	73,466,840,201.25	0.7	2.93%
35	YOBE	29,230,547,154.25	27,465,573,418.77	0.1	0.70%
36	ZAMFARA	79,286,884,618.37	61,716,954,035.15	0.3	1.89%
37	FCT	101,949,645,786.10	132,195,733,234.70	(0.2)	2.43%
Total		4,189,699,078,909.01	3,966,219,816,141.57	5.6%	100.00%

Note:

1 Domestic Debt Stock for Twenty Eight (28) States: Abia, Adamawa, Akwa Ibom, Anambra, Bauchi, Bayelsa, Benue, Borno, Cross River, Delta, Ebonyi, Edo, Ekiti, Enugu, Gombe, Imo, Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Katsina, Kebbi, Kogi, Kwara, Lagos, Nasarawa, Niger, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Plateau, Sokoto, Taraba, Yobe, Zamfara and the FCT as at June 30, 2020.

2* Domestic Debt Stock Figures for Rivers State were as at December 31, 2018

Federal Government Actual Domestic Debt Service for Second Quarter, 2020					Federal Government Actual Domestic Debt Service for Second Quarter, 2019					% Change of Interest Payment in Domestic Debt Service Q1, 2020 & Q4, 2019
(Amount in Naira)					(Amount in Naira)					
Instruments	April	May	June	Total	Instruments	April	May	June	Total	
NTBs					NTBs					
Interest	25,970,431,060.35	5,856,405,366.18	11,799,416,906.39	43,626,253,332.92	Interest	14,897,947,747.19	14,700,317,313.85	16,113,483,121.45	45,711,748,182.49	(0.05)
Federal Govt. Bonds				-	Federal Govt. Bonds				-	-
Interest	202,191,929,521.11	31,886,342,240.96		234,078,271,762.07	Interest	69,184,981,715.55	31,779,137,060.69	28,027,002,739.73	128,991,121,515.97	0.81
Treasury Bonds				-	Treasury Bonds				-	-
Interest				-	Interest	-	3,125,000,000.00	3,125,000,000.00	6,250,000,000.00	-
Principal			25000000000	25,000,000,000.00	Principal	-	-	-	-	-
FGNSB				-	FGNSB				-	-
Interest	162,049,612.61	131,339,036.76	131,907,561.70	425,296,211.07	Interest	112,381,123.27	100,208,236.88	98,031,264.55	310,620,624.70	0.37
FGN Sukuk				-	FGN SUKUK				-	-
Rentals				-	Rentals				0.00	-
Interest			7,871,971,382.59	7,871,971,382.59	Interest	-	-	7,849,934,246.58	7,849,934,246.58	0.00
FGN Green Bond				-	FGN Green Bond				-	-
Interest			1808423210	1,808,423,210.29	Interest			718,532,010.96	718,532,010.96	1.52
TOTAL INTEREST	228,324,410,194.07	37,874,086,643.90	46,611,719,060.97	312,810,215,898.94	TOTAL INTEREST	84,195,310,586.01	49,704,662,611.42	55,931,983,383.27	189,831,956,580.70	64.8%

Note:

(I) TOTAL INTEREST EXCLUDES THE SINKING FUND CHARGES OF N161,092,250.00 IN RESPECT OF TREASURY BONDS (MANAGED BY THE CBN)

(II) TOTAL DOMESTIC DEBT SERVICE ARE PROVISIONAL SUBJECT TO RECONCILIATION AND SIGN-OFF WITH THE CBN & OAGF

Nigeria's External Debt Stock as at June 30, 2020
in Millions of USD

Category	Outstanding Debt	Percentage of Total
MULTILATERAL		
International Monetary Fund	3,358.90	
World Bank Group		
International Development Association	10,053.66	
Int'l Bank for Reconstruction and Devpt.	409.51	
African Development Bank Group		
African Development Bank	1,325.72	
Africa Growing Together Fund	0.14	
African Development Fund	921.91	
Arab Bank for Economic Development in Africa	5.88	
European Development Fund	52.52	
Islamic Development Bank	30.22	
Int'l Fund For Agricultural Development	201.68	
SUB-TOTAL	16,360.14	51.97%
BILATERAL		
China (Exim Bank of China)	3,240.73	
France (Agence Francaise Development)	403.65	
Japan (Japan International Cooperation Agency)	76.69	
India (Exim Bank of India)	34.87	
Germany (Kreditanstalt Fur Wiederaufbua)	192.71	
SUB-TOTAL	3,948.65	12.54%
COMMERCIAL		
Eurobonds	10,868.35	
Diaspora Bond	300.00	
SUB-TOTAL	11,168.35	35.48%
GRAND TOTAL	31,477.14	100.00%

**ACTUAL EXTERNAL DEBT SERVICE PAYMENTS APRIL - JUNE, 2020
IN THOUSANDS OF USD**

CATEGORY		Interest	Service	Deferred	Deferred	Deferred	Overdue Charges	Waiver/ Credit	Commitment Charges	Other Charges	Total	Percentage
	Principal	Fee	Fee	Principal	Interest	Service	Indemnity					of Total
MULTILATERAL	61,163.45	17,721.59	13,818.84	0.00	78.58	207.43	615.75	(38.20)	1343.62	0.00	94,911.07	33%
IBRD	0.00	6,368.16	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	6,368.16	
A.D.B	13,333.33	5,293.53	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	532.93	0.00	19,159.79	
IFAD	0.00	165.27	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	165.27	
A.D.F	929.02	509.30	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	362.24	0.00	1,800.56	
IDA	44,812.01	5,220.04	13,809.60	0.00	78.58	207.43	0.00	(36.86)	448.45	0.00	64,539.26	
EDF	1,495.57	165.29	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1,660.86	
BADEA	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
IDB	593.52	0.00	9.24	0.00	0.00	0.00	615.75	(1.34)	0.00	0.00	1,217.17	
BILATERAL	9,107.39	4,221.80	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	-226.71	1,157.71	0.00	14,260.19	5%
EXIM BANK OF CHINA	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Nigeria Communication Sattelite	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Nigeria National Public Security Comm. Sys. Project	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Nigeria Railway Modernisation Project(Idu Kaduna Section)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Nigeria Railway Modernisation Project(Lagos - Ibadan Section)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Nigeria Abuja Light Rail Project	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Nigeria ICT Infrastructure Backbone Project	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Nigeria Four Airport Terminals Expansion Project	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Nigerian Zungeru Hydroelectric Project	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Nigerian Rehabilitation and Upgrading of Abuja-Keffi-Makurdi Road Project	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
EXIM BANK OF INDIA	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
FRENCH DEVELOPMENT AGENCY (AFD)	9,107.39	4,177.46	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	(226.71)	1,157.71	0.00	14,215.85	
JICA	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
KFW	0.00	44.34	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	44.34	
COMMERCIAL	0.00	157,012.17	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	157,012.17	55%
EUROBONDS	0.00	148,574.67	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	148,574.67	
7.625% Eurobond 2025	0.00	42,637.17	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	42,637.17	
6.5% Eurobond 2027	0.00	48,750.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	48,750.00	
7.625% Eurobond 2047	0.00	57,187.50	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	57,187.50	
DIASPORA BOND	0.00	8,437.50	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	8,437.50	
OTHERS	0.00	20,859.63	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	20,859.63	7%
Agency Fee	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
OIL WARRANT	0.00	20,859.63	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	20,859.63	
TOTAL	70,270.84	199,815.19	13,818.84	-	78.58	207.43	615.75	(264.91)	2,501.33	-	287,043.07	100%

States, FCT and Federal Governments' External Debt Stock
as at 30th June, 2020

S/No	States and FGN	Multilateral	Bilateral (AFD)	Bilateral (CHINA EXIM BANK, JICA, INDIA, KFW)	Commercial	Total
		USD	USD	USD	Eurobonds & Diaspora Bonds USD	USD
1	Abia	87,154,702.46	-	-	-	87,154,702.46
2	Adamawa	98,976,511.58	6,500,000.00		-	105,476,511.58
3	Akwa Ibom	46,619,779.74	-		-	46,619,779.74
4	Anambra	115,886,392.46	-		-	115,886,392.46
5	Bauchi	129,449,049.24	-		-	129,449,049.24
6	Bayelsa	51,312,525.84	-		-	51,312,525.84
7	Benue	29,069,437.68	-		-	29,069,437.68
8	Borno	20,020,197.01	-		-	20,020,197.01
9	Cross River	107,281,922.84	43,900,000.00	21,464,442.18	-	172,646,365.02
10	Delta	53,856,648.90	-		-	53,856,648.90
11	Ebonyi	59,127,695.49	-			59,127,695.49
12	Edo	245,192,506.17	-		-	245,192,506.17
13	Ekiti	90,702,124.75	-		-	90,702,124.75
14	Enugu	108,558,813.78	6,500,000.00		-	115,058,813.78
15	Gombe	35,200,627.45	-		-	35,200,627.45
16	Imo	23,306,075.58	27,911,517.88		-	51,217,593.46
17	Jigawa	29,555,191.42	-		-	29,555,191.42
18	Kaduna	554,543,449.75	-	15,535,692.17	-	570,079,141.92
19	Kano	60,485,778.07	3,369,600.00		-	63,855,378.07
20	Katsina	74,995,625.44	-		-	74,995,625.44
21	Kebbi	42,012,518.94	-		-	42,012,518.94
22	Kogi	28,629,302.18	-		-	28,629,302.18
23	Kwara	43,426,265.98	-		-	43,426,265.98
24	Lagos	1,117,394,751.98	143,830,000.00		-	1,261,224,751.98
25	Nassarawa	55,823,034.28	-		-	55,823,034.28
26	Niger	66,003,904.55	12,500,000.00		-	78,503,904.55
27	Ogun	89,614,146.87	8,294,600.00		-	97,908,746.87
28	Ondo	74,792,475.77	5,000,000.00		-	79,792,475.77
29	Osun	78,140,931.31	12,245,989.00		-	90,386,920.31
30	Oyo	82,509,495.08	-		-	82,509,495.08
31	Plateau	28,126,343.15	5,000,000.00		-	33,126,343.15
32	Rivers	69,534,420.77	-		-	69,534,420.77
33	Sokoto	34,661,496.13	-		-	34,661,496.13
34	Taraba	34,641,916.22	-		-	34,641,916.22
35	Yobe	25,669,384.57	-		-	25,669,384.57
36	Zamfara	29,638,974.33	-		-	29,638,974.33
37	FCT	29,084,778.83	-		-	29,084,778.83
	Sub-Total State & FCT	3,950,999,196.60	275,051,706.88	37,000,134.35	-	4,263,051,037.83
	FGN	11,999,630,103.40	134,455,393.12	3,911,643,765.65	11,168,352,000.00	27,214,081,262.17
	Grand Total	15,950,629,300.00	409,507,100.00	3,948,643,900.00	11,168,352,000.00	31,477,132,300.00
	Percentage of States & FCT to Grand Total					14%
	Percentage of FGN to Grand Total					86%

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Contact Us

 @nigerianstat

 NBSNigeria

 www.nigerianstat.gov.ng

 Head Office Address
Plot 762, Independence Avenue, Central
Business District, FCT, Abuja Nigeria.

 +234 803 386 5388

 feedback@nigerianstat.gov.ng